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D1-Glia

Astrocyte D1 Receptor Signalling in Depression

Data Management Plan

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Table of Contents

Introduction	3
Project Data.....	3
Acknowledgement.....	3
1. Data Summary	4
Purpose of the data collection/generation	4
Relation to the objectives of the project.....	4
Types and formats of data generated/collected	4
Re-use of existing data	5
Origin of the data.....	5
Expected size of the data	5
The data utility: to whom will it be useful	5
2. FAIR data	5
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	5
Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	5
Metadata of the data supporting the project will be uploaded. By doing so, their original data sources can be traced.....	5
Identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism	5
Naming conventions.....	5
Approach towards search keyword	6
Approach for clear versioning.....	6
Standards for Metadata Creation.....	6
2.2 Making Data Accessible	7
Data Access Strategy.....	7
Methods or software tools needed to access the data.....	7
Depository for the data and associated metadata, documentation and code.....	7
Provision of access in case of any restrictions.....	8
2.3 Making data interoperable	8
Interoperability of data (the use of data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability)	8
Use of standard vocabulary for all data types for inter-disciplinary interoperability	8
2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	8
Licensing data to permit the widest reuse possible	8
Timing for Data Reuse and Embargo Periods.....	8
Third-Party Data Use and Restrictions.....	8
Data quality assurance processes	8
Length of time for which the data will remain re-usable	9
3. Allocation of resources.....	9
Costs estimate for making data FAIR	9
Responsibilities for data management in the project.....	9
4. Data security	9
Data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data.....	9
5. Ethical aspects.....	9
Data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data.....	9
6. Other	9
Use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.....	9

Introduction

The focus of D1-Glia is on astrocytes, a type of neuroglial cell in the central nervous system, and the neurotransmitter dopamine. We used advanced techniques to investigate the interaction between dopamine and astrocytes, with the aim of providing new insights into the pathology of Major depressive disorder (MDD). Data will be generated using both novel and established research methodologies and will be compared with existing data at the Laboratory of Neuroendocrinology-Molecular Cell Physiology (LN-MCP) at the Faculty of Medicine. This Data Management Plan (Version 3) reflects updates and necessary revisions made during the project lifecycle to the data management and sharing strategy initially outlined (which aimed for full data deposition on Zenodo), adapting to practical considerations while adhering to FAIR principles. If the project yields potential targets for new therapies, commercial potential will be evaluated and appropriate protective measures considered.

Project Data

Data Set:

<i>Data Set (DS)</i>	<i>Contains (see Data Summary)</i>
DS_D1-Glia_FRETcAMP	• Experiment Data_Colibri7
DS_D1-Glia_FRETlactate	• Experiment Data_LSM780
DS_D1-Glia_Fluo4Ca	• Experiment Data_LSM800
DS_D1-Glia_STED	• Experiment Data_STED
DS_D1-Glia_PCR	• Experiment Data_PCR

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1. Data Summary

Purpose of the data collection/generation

All data will be collected for the purpose of addressing specific research questions within the D1-Glia project, which aims to understand how dopamine is linked to astrocyte function. At the LN-MCP, we will generate data using nanosensors and super-resolution microscopy to investigate how key molecules change under different experimental conditions.

Relation to the objectives of the project

This project aims to explore the role of dopamine in astrocyte function by analyzing molecular changes. Through data collection at LN-MCP, we seek to identify key aspects of dopamine in astrocytes and their potential implications.

Types and formats of data generated/collected

The project generates various data types, primarily:

(A) Raw Experimental Data: Raw multidimensional images, primarily in the instrument's native format (e.g., .czi, potentially .obf for STED), including associated instrument and measurement metadata from fluorescence microscopy systems (FRET, Fluo4, STED). Raw numerical data from qPCR experiments (e.g., Ct values exported as .xlsx or .csv) are also generated.

(B) Derived Experimental Data: Processed images (e.g., standard formats like .tiff, .jpeg) and derived numerical data (e.g., spreadsheets like .xlsx, or .csv) resulting from initial processing of raw data (e.g., using imaging software or initial qPCR calculations).

(C) Analysed Experimental Data: Numerical data (e.g., .xlsx, .csv) resulting from scientific analysis, such as quantification from STED images (e.g., particle counts, distances) or calculated qPCR results (e.g., relative expression levels). Analyses use common tools (e.g., spreadsheets, image analysis software like ImageJ/FIJI, scripting languages like Python, qPCR analysis software). Analysis workflows may generate scripts.

(D) Statistical Data: Outputs from statistical analysis performed on data derived from all experimental types (FRET, Fluo4, STED, PCR), including numerical results, tables, and graphical representations (e.g., statistical software project files, image files, presentation slides).

(E) Documentation: Systematic file naming conventions are applied (details available in internal documentation). Project deliverables (DMPs, reports, drafts) are typically in .docx or .pdf format.

Re-use of existing data

1. Existing data at LN-MCP: We may compare new findings against previously collected data (e.g., MATLAB scripts, existing protocols).
2. Publicly-available Programs: We may use existing software programs from the website to generate analysed data (e.g., FRET signals, Fluo4-AM intensity).

Origin of the data

1. All Data sets: Generated at the LN-MCP.
2. Existing FRET and Fluo4-AM data: Retrieved from the LN-MCP's NAS server.

Expected size of the data

1. FRET and Fluo4-AM: Up to ~500GB each.
2. Scientific publications and other documents: Up to ~100MB in total.

The data utility: to whom will it be useful

The D1-Glia research data holds broad relevance and serves as a vital resource. Researchers looking to employ similar methodologies will find this data helpful. Pharmaceutical companies involved in drug discovery and development may utilise the data to identify potential drug targets. Science journalists may introduce the data to highlight recent advancements in the field. Lastly, the publicly accessible project documents provide information to other groups supported by the Horizon Europe Project.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

Metadata supporting the project will be uploaded. By doing so, their original data sources can be traced.

Identifiability of data and refer to the standard identification mechanism

To improve data findability, a descriptive README file containing comprehensive metadata has been deposited in the Zenodo repository. This ensures the generated data (detailed in the README) is discoverable.

Naming conventions

Data files naming for the D1-Glia project will follow this convention:

- Data set: DS_D1-Glia_[data set title]
- Experiment Data (A-D: see Table 1):
 - (A-B): xxx_[experiment title]_[condition]_yyyymmdd
 - (C-D): analysis_[experiment title]_[condition]

For C and D, since the first column in C's Excel sheet contains names corresponding to A, the file name does not include the date. Regarding D, as all data also originates from C, the date is not included in the file name.

- Project deliverable: [Deliverable number]_D1-Glia_yyyymmdd

File names created from this naming convention are composed of several parts, each separated by an underscore (_). There should be no spaces in the file name.

Details about these parts are given below:

- xxx: A running number for individual measurements.
- [experiment or document title]: A brief title reflecting the content.
- yyyymmdd: The date when the data was created.
- [condition]: Details about the content of the experiment, such as the drugs used.

Experimental data will be stored in a folder structure, sorted by year, month, and date. Data Generation (A) will be organised so that the file name tells the experiment, date and serial number, all traceable to the lab books.

Approach towards the search keyword

Keywords will be incorporated in the metadata to maximise discoverability.

Approach for clear versioning

Major versions of the experimental datasets will be assigned version numbers (e.g., V1, V2), with a summary of the Change history recorded for each version.

Standards for Metadata Creation

A standardised metadata format will be provided as follows:

- Publication date
- Working Title
- Authors: names, Affiliations, Contact information, ORCID
- Description: Details on data collection methodology, data treatment and control measures, definitions of variables, measurement units, models, experimental details etc.
- Version
- Language
- Keywords
- Grants
- Related/alternate identifiers of publications and datasets

Zenodo, our chosen platform, supports the DataCite Metadata Schema v4, which provides comprehensive and detailed metadata that facilitates access to data. Furthermore, Zenodo will provide standard formats of metadata: MARCXML, Dublin Core (in accordance with OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, and JSON-LD (Schema.org).

2.2 Making Data Accessible

Data Access Strategy

The project initially intended to deposit all raw imaging datasets in Zenodo. However, this was reconsidered in light of practical considerations related to data volume and long-term management. Instead, to ensure transparency and discoverability, a comprehensive README file with metadata describing the datasets, along with the final version of the Data Management Plan, has been deposited in Zenodo.

- **Raw Data Access:** Large imaging datasets (e.g. .czi files) are securely stored on the institutional NAS server at LN-MCP and can be provided upon reasonable request to the authors or host institution for verification or reuse purposes.
- **Analysis Protocol Access:** The project relied on well-established workflows. Access to more detailed analytical procedures or scripts can be granted upon request if required for reproducibility.
- **Results and Methods:** Key findings and essential methods will be made openly available through a forthcoming bioRxiv preprint and subsequent peer-reviewed publications.
- **Standard Experimental Protocols:** Routine laboratory protocols (e.g. for cell culture or staining procedures) are documented and can be shared upon request to facilitate reproducibility.

Methods or software tools needed to access the data

The metadata provided on Zenodo (in the README file) describes the general types of software tools required to interpret the data (e.g., imaging software viewers for .czi, spreadsheet software, statistical packages).

Depository for the data and associated metadata, documentation and code.

Metadata (in the README file) is deposited on Zenodo. Full raw datasets are stored on the secure LN-MCP NAS server. Analysis code, where applicable and not subject to restriction, is stored alongside the data on the NAS. Publications will also be deposited in the University of Ljubljana Repository.

Provision of access in case of any restrictions.

Access to data (raw data, standard protocols) is provided upon reasonable request directed to the authors/host institution. Requests will be evaluated based on the justification provided. Access to certain analysis workflows remains restricted due to strategic reasons.

2.3 Making data interoperable

Interoperability of data (the use of data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability)

We use widely adopted software for data access and analysis. The README file deposited on Zenodo provides metadata details to aid interpretation.

Use of standard vocabulary for all data types for inter-disciplinary interoperability

Not relevant to the datasets yielded within the D1-Glia project.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Licensing data to permit the widest reuse possible

The metadata/README file deposited on Zenodo is licensed under CC-BY 4.0. Raw datasets and analysis protocols are available upon request and will be shared under mutually agreed terms.

Timing for Data Reuse and Embargo Periods

Access to underlying data is upon reasonable request with no fixed embargo period, subject to evaluation of the request. Results will be shared promptly via a preprint on bioRxiv.

Third-Party Data Use and Restrictions

Reuse of data obtained upon request must comply with the CC-BY licence and any additional terms agreed with the data provider.

Data quality assurance processes

LN-MCP complies with ISO 17025 quality standards and adheres to Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) guidelines for certain sections of LN-MCP.

Length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

Metadata on Zenodo is preserved long-term. Data stored on the LN-MCP NAS server will be maintained according to institutional data retention policies, typically for at least 5-10 years post-project.

3. Allocation of resources

Cost estimate for making data FAIR

The project will not incur any direct costs for making our data FAIR.

Responsibilities for data management in the project

Data management during the project implementation phase was primarily handled by the ERA fellow Dr. Keita Sugiyama under the supervision of Prof. Robert Zorec. Following the completion of the fellowship, the long-term responsibility for data curation, preservation, and managing access requests according to the policies outlined in this plan resides with the host laboratory (LN-MCP, University of Ljubljana), coordinated by the project supervisor.

4. Data security

Data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

Data will be stored on the computer disk where the measurements were taken and, as mentioned, on the lab's NAS server. If the data involves intellectual property protection, access will be restricted to individuals involved in the patent application process.

5. Ethical aspects

Data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

Not applicable; no personal or sensitive data are collected.

6. Other

Use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management

We will deposit scientific publications related to the D1-Glia project in the Repository of the University of Ljubljana. This repository, adhering to the OpenAIRE repository guidelines and providing interfaces in both Slovenian and English, will ensure full open access.